

Agroforestry Voluntary Carbon Market

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Contribution of different elements of a forest (trunks, branches, leaves, soil) to carbon sequestration

Forests are ecosystems able of removing carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere and storing it in natural 'reservoirs' (trunks, branches, leaves, soil) through a process called carbon sequestration. Forestry and agroforestry systems can sequester between 5 and 10 Mg of CO₂ per hectare and year, depending on factors such as the species, growth rate, density and environmental factors (temperature, rainfall and radiation). The European Union has set itself the target of achieving net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050. This commitment means that all emissions must be offset by actions that remove an equivalent amount of CO₂, such as carbon sequestration or other technologies. This context creates new opportunities for forestry producers, who can be financially rewarded for their contribution to carbon sequestration. In 2023, Portugal established a voluntary carbon market, following the example of other countries, with the aim of incentivizing projects that reduce or capture emissions in forest, agricultural or landscape areas, and is currently awaiting regulation. This system will allow forestry producers to receive additional financial compensation for the management of their forests through afforestation, conservation and the adoption of sustainable practices, generating carbon credits now or in the future. Each carbon credit corresponds to one Megagram or tonne of CO₂ captured. These credits are then available on a dedicated platform to be marketed to companies that need to offset their emissions. The platform is managed by ADENE (the Public Institution National Energy Agency), ensuring that the entire process is verified and transparent. The value of a tonne of carbon on the market depends on the emissions trading system and market conditions. In the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), the largest carbon market in the world, prices have shown significant fluctuations in recent years (February 2023 - €100 Mg, January 2025 - €77 Mg).

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